

was refluxed for 60 h in a Dean—Stark apparatus. The cooled reaction mixture was successively washed with distilled water, 5% sodium bicarbonate and distilled water. The organic layer was dried (anhydrous Na₂SO₄), filtered and the solvent removed to yield a deep brown crystalline residue. Most of the unreacted benzoyl acetone was removed by fractional crystallisation from petroleum ether. The mother liquor was evaporated to dryness to yield a crude material (70 g).

Separation of 3, 4 and 5: By column chromatography: The crude material (500 mg) was chromatographed on silica gel (60–120 mesh, B D H) and eluted with petroleum ether—ethyl acetate (9:1). The process separated among others, the unreacted benzoyl acetone (250 mg) and the titled cyclohexenones, 3 (12 mg) and 4 (9 mg) as yellowish viscous liquid, while the isomer 5 (6 mg) as a deep brown semi-solid.

By preparative tlc: The crude reaction product (500 mg) was resolved by preparative tlc in petroleum ether—ethyl acetate (9:1) into 3 (*R_f* 0.77), 4 (*R_f* 0.40) and 5 (*R_f* 0.14), their yields being 10, 8 and 6%, respectively, and benzoylacetone.

4-Acetyl-5,5 dimethyl-3-phenylcyclohex-2-enone (3): It showed ν_{max} (neat) 1705 (CO—CH₃), 1650 (α,β -unsaturated-ketone), 1575, 1550 (ph. gr.), 175, 1350 cm⁻¹ (*gem* dimethyl); λ_{max} (EtOH) 248 nm; δ 1.17 (3H) and 1.56 (3H) (*gem*-dimethyl), 1.82 (3H, —CO—CH₃), 2.00 (1H, d) and 2.47 (1H, d) (*J* 16.0 Hz, methylene protons), 4.50 (1H, CH), 5.53 (1H, =CH) and 7.53–7.93 (5H, m, ArH); *m/z* 243 (*M*+1) (5%), 227(100%), 199(3%), 185(5%), 105 (43%), 77(35%) and 43(18%); 2,4-DNP (m.p. 128–30°).

4-Benzoyl-3,5,5-trimethylcyclohex-2-enone (4): It showed ν_{max} (neat) 1655 (C=O), 1590, 1575 (ph. gr.), 1365, 1330 cm⁻¹ (*gem*-dimethyl); λ_{max} (EtOH) 246 nm; δ 1.05 (3H) and 1.12 (3H) (*gem*-dimethyl), 2.00 (3H, =CCH₃), 1.95 (1H, d) and 2.90 (1H, d) (*J* 16.0 Hz, methylene protons), 4.27 (1H, CH), 5.89 (1H, =CH), 7.54–7.95 (5H, m, ArH); *m/z* 243 (*M*+1) (14%), 227(6%), 137(4%), 105(100%), 77(10%) and 65(2%); 2,4-DNP (m.p. 124–26°).

6-Benzoyl-3,5,5-trimethylcyclohex-2-enone (5): It showed ν_{max} (neat) 1655 (C=O), 1592, 1575 (ph. ring), 1370, 1335 cm⁻¹ (*gem*-dimethyl); λ_{max} (EtOH) 250 nm; δ 0.94 (3H) and 1.16 (3H) (*gem*-dimethyl), 1.85 (3H, =CCH₃), 2.03 (1H, d) and 2.85 (1H, d) (*J* 15.5 Hz, methylene protons), 4.19 (1H, CH), 6.0 (1H, =CH), 7.90–8.04 (5H, m, ArH); *m/z* 243 (*M*+1) (10%), 227(3%), 137(3%), 105 (100%), 77(70%) and 65(4%); 2,4-DNP (m.p. 121–23°).

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Fragmentation Pathways in the Mass Spectra of 2-Methylisoflavone Derivatives. Useful in their Diagnosis

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ISOFLAVONES, an important group of natural products, occur widely in the plant kingdom and many of them possess oestrogenic, antitumoral and insecticidal properties^{1,2}. 2-Methylisoflavones are now coming into prominence as the first examples of their occurrence in plants have been reported^{3,4} in recent years only. These compounds seem to be important also because they are almost twice as toxic as the corresponding 2-substituted-isoflavones⁵. No detailed record of the mass spectral fragmentation of the natural analogues (hydroxy or methoxy substituted) of 2-methylisoflavones has been published so far. We have earlier reported⁶ the fragmentation pattern of the synthetic samples of a few acetyl and allyl substituted derivatives. The present paper discusses the results of the mass spectrometric investigations of seven differently substituted 2-methylisoflavones and the utility of these studies in the structure elucidation of this important class of compounds.

The isoflavones (1–7) used in this study were purified by preparative tlc and/or crystallisation, and the purity was > 99%. The low resolution electron impact mass spectra of all the seven samples were carried out with a Swedish LKB instrument of the USSR Academy of Sciences, Moscow. Mass spectra were recorded by direct insertion with the inlet temperatures maintained between 40 and 70°, and an electron energy of 70 eV.

- 1; R¹-H, R²-H, R³-H, R⁴-H
 2; R¹-CH₃, R²-H, R³-H, R⁴-H
 3; R¹-H, R²-H, R³-H, R⁴-OCH₃
 4; R¹-H, R²-H, R³-H, R⁴-OCH₃, R⁵-OCH₃
 5; R¹-CH₃, R²-OH, R³-H, R⁴-OH
 6; R¹-CH₃, R²-OH, R³-H, R⁴-OCH₃
 7; R¹-CH₃, R²-OCH₃, R³-H, R⁴-OCH₃

The prominent and important fragments observed in the mass spectra of all the seven compounds are summarised in Table 1. It is seen that the methyl group at position C-2 in the isoflavone molecule induces significant changes in the mass spectra of these compounds which could be of considerable diagnostic importance.

TABLE 1—PROMINENT AND IMPORTANT FRAGMENTS IN THE MASS SPECTRA OF 1-7

Compd. no.	Fragments <i>m/z</i> (rel. int %)				
1	252 (76), 116 (6)	251 (100), 115 (15)	137 (8)	136 (5)	126 (5)
2	266 (92), 165 (10), 133 (8)	265 (100), 152 (12), 122 (30)	250 (6), 151 (21), 116 (13)	222 (13), 150 (20), 115 (50)	194 (5), 141 (5), 108 (6)
3	282 (100), 141 (6), 137 (7)	281 (90), 131 (7)	267 (9), 103 (7)	146 (16), 103 (7)	145 (1), 77 (7)
4	312 (100), 281 (8), 175 (1)	311 (81), 269 (7), 161 (5)	298 (6), 267 (5), 156 (6)	297 (24), 226 (8), 141 (5)	283 (5), 176 (3), 127 (6)
5	298 (100), 281 (52), 149 (10)	297 (27), 269 (6), 148 (30)	284 (13), 267 (6), 147 (14)	283 (67), 228 (5)	282 (14), 151 (50)
6	312 (100), 295 (57), 151 (16)	311 (25), 283 (6), 147 (17)	298 (13), 163 (7), 126 (5)	297 (70), 162 (52), 91 (5)	296 (13), 156 (7)
7	326 (27), 295 (100), 133 (5)	325 (2), 280 (5)	312 (4), 176 (5)	311 (23), 175 (2)	297 (7), 163 (3), 151 (7)

The molecular ions in all the seven 2-methylisoflavones also appear as doubly charged ions (M^{++} at m/z 126 (5) for 1, 133 (8) for 2, 141 (6) for 3, 156 (6) for 4, 149 (10) for 5, 156 (7) for 6, 163 (3) for 7), thus reflecting the stability of these aromatic systems. Another characteristic feature is the formation of ($M-1$)⁺ fragment (of the type 8 involving C-4 carbonyl group and the loss of C-2' hydrogen) in all the seven compounds; in isoflavones devoid of the 2-methyl group this fragment usually does not appear⁷. In simpler 2-methylisoflavones, not carrying any substituent in the side phenyl ring of the molecule (compounds 1 and 2), ($M-1$)⁺ forms the base peak. Substitution in the side phenyl ring (compounds 3-7) brings down the intensity of the ($M-1$)⁺ ion making (M)⁺ the base peak (except compound 7). In compounds 5-7, carrying the C-2' hydroxy or methoxy

function, the intensity of the ($M-1$)⁺ peak (2-27%) is much lower than in compounds 3 and 4 (80-90%). This could be very useful in distinguishing a C-2' OH or OCH₃ substituent from a C-4' substituent in 2-methylisoflavones.

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It is significant to note that the 2-methyl group is unexpectedly stable to electron impact. However, in the presence of a 2'-oxygenated functional group, the 2 methyl group is lost due to the formation of a furan ring system at the positions C-2 and C-2'. 2'-Hydroxy-2-methylisoflavones 5 and 6 under electron impact first lose the C-2 methyl radical (m/z 283 (67) for 5, 297 (70) for 6) followed by the loss of a hydrogen atom forming the ions 9 and 10, respectively. 2'-Methoxy-2-methylisoflavone (7) produces two successive losses of methyl radicals forming the ion 11. Thus the formation of similar fragments could be characteristic for the presence of a 2'-hydroxyl or 2'-methoxyl group in 2-methylisoflavones.

- 9; (R = H) m/z 282 (14)
 10; (R = CH₃) m/z 296 (13)
 11; (R = CH₃) m/z 296 (20)

Another significant effect of a 2-methyl group is in the Diels-Alder retro-addition of these compounds under electron impact. Isoflavones without the 2-methyl substituent generally give two ketene fragments and one acetylene fragment⁸; however, a few isoflavones carrying the 2'-methoxyl group show two acetylene fragments⁹. But all the seven 2-methylisoflavones studied now show two phenyl-acetylene fragments (m/z 116 (6) and 115 (15) for 1, 116 (13) and 115 (50) for 2, 146 (16) and 145 (1) for 3, 176 (3) and 175 (1) for 4, 148 (30) and 147 (14) for 5, 162 (52) and 161 (4) for 6, 176 (5) and 175 (2) for 7) in their mass spectra.

Besides the above important fragments, many other fragments due to the losses of hydrogen, methyl, carbon monoxide, aldehyde and methoxyl groups, etc. were also observed in the mass spectra of these seven compounds. The results presented in this study could be of special help in the identification and characterisation of natural or new 2-methylisoflavones.

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Fatty Acids from Anacardiaceae Seed Oils

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SEEDS from *Rhus wallichii* and *Choerospondias axillaris* belonging to the family Anacardiaceae have been analysed for the oil contents, and their fatty acid composition was determined using tlc-glc techniques.

presence of conjugated double bonds was ruled out with the help of uv-analysis. The picric acid tlc test^a for epoxy function and Halphen test^b for cyclopropenoid moiety in both the oils were found to be negative. Both the oils contained the common fatty acids in varying proportions (Table 1). In the oil from *C. axillaris*, the percentage of linoleic acid, an essential fatty acid, was as high as ~61% which is of great importance from the point of view of nutrition. However, low oil content (8%) may affect potential utility of this species. *R. wallichii* was found to contain the amount of palmitic acid (~70%), higher than ever reported in any other species. This species with moderate oil content (~13%) may be profitably used for the manufacture of detergents, surfactants, lubricants and in confectionary products.

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TABLE 1—ANALYTICAL AND PHYSICAL DATA OF SEEDS AND OILS

Source	Oil content %	I.V.	S.V.	Component acids (wt. %) by glc						
				12:0	14:0	16:0	18:0	18:1	18:2	18:3
<i>C. axillaris</i>	8.1	139.5	195.5	—	—	11.0	0.6	27.1	60.7	0.5
<i>R. wallichii</i>	12.7	50.9	207.6	0.5	0.8	69.8	0.8	6.8	20.6	0.8

I.V. = Iodine value, S.V. = saponification value.

Experimental

The air-dried seeds were powdered and extracted thoroughly with petroleum ether (b.p. 40–60°). The solvents were removed under vacuum at 40° to obtain the oil. The analytical values of oil and seeds were determined according to the procedures recommended by the AOCS¹. Ir and uv spectra of oils were recorded with the help of a Perkin-Elmer 621 and a Beckman DK-2A spectrophotometer, respectively. A Perkin-Elmer 154 analytical gas chromatograph equipped with a thermal detector using DEGS column (220°) with nitrogen as a carrier gas was used for fatty acid analysis.

The ir spectra of the oils had absorption peaks at 3000s and 1650w cm⁻¹, indicating ordinary unsaturation. There was no peak in the regions of trans-unsaturation and/or unusual functions. The

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Essential Oil of Indian *Cryptomeria japonica*

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CRYPTOMERIA *japonica*, an exotic from Japan, is an evergreen tree cultivated as plantation in the northern part of Bengal. In contrast to the